

THE UTILISATION OF ELECTRONIC MEDIA FOR ARTISTIC SKILL ACQUISITION: THE FOUNDATION OF ALL LEARNING IN EDUCATION.

IDONGESIT AKAN UDI (Ph.D.)
Department of Educational Technology
Faculty of Education, University of Uyo
idongesitaudi@gmail.com
+2348076778596

Abstract

This research examines the utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition and the extent to which it is used by teachers in Akwa Ibom State. The study was guided by three objectives, three research questions and three hypotheses. The population of the study included both teachers in secondary and post-secondary levels of education in Akwa Ibom State. Multi-stage random sampling was used to select 500 teachers comprising 200 secondary school teachers, 100 lecturers in colleges of education and 200 lecturers in public universities in Akwa Ibom State. An instrument entitled “Utilisation of Electronic Media for Artistic Skill Acquisition Questionnaire (UEMASAQ)” developed by the researcher was used in data collection. The instrument was validated by experts and the reliability of the instrument yielded Cronbach Alpha of 0.73. Data obtained were analysed using mean, standard deviation and independent t-test at the 0.05 level of significance. Result reveals low level of utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition among the teachers. The result also shows that there is no significant difference in the utilisation of electronic media between male and female teachers, while there was a significant difference in electronic media utilisation in terms of age. For experience, less experienced teachers reported better utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition than experienced teachers ($p < .05$). Therefore, the study recommends, among others, better training and re-orientation of teachers on how to harness the potentials in electronic media in enhancing their artistic skill acquisition and their quality of instructional delivery and consequently students’ academic performance.

Keywords: Artistic skill, acquisition, electronic, media

Introduction

Artistic skills play significant role in all facets of learning. It plays a major role in the development of a child and also facilitates effective teaching and learning process.

Tsimboukidou (2010) while stressing the significant role of artistic skills in teaching and learning, observed that artistic skills help to develop better understanding, confidence and communication skills while also allowing students to express themselves. In the word of Kear & Callaway (2000), teachers' artistic potentials facilitate students' engagement by enabling them to communicate through images and thereby, making learning more interactive as it facilitates their level of assimilation. Similarly, Riley (2012) observed that artistic skills have the capacity to develop children's thinking skills, organisational levels and reasoning abilities. This is because the use of artistic skills could help to increase active engagement of the students during teaching. Burrill (2010) opined that these competencies could help teachers to organise various hands-on tasks in which students or learners are given opportunities to explore, discover and create themselves, promoting their cognitive skills.

One of the ways of improving the artistic skills is through the utilisation of electronic media. Udi and Nwosu (2023) affirm that almost everyone would agree to the fact that technology has become the driving factor in every phase of life, especially in education. That technology applied to Fine Art Education would improve creativeness through the transformation and manipulation of the art already created by the students. Electronic media as described by Koert (2000) are a number of equipment or materials inter-connected or inter-related in lubricating and can include all instructional media that are electronically generated. The lists of electronic media include television, projectors, tape recorders, video sets, radio, internet facilities, computers and telecommunication facilities. They are very useful in teaching and learning processes as they help create new learning environment that positively motivates students (Pintrich and Schunk, 2002). Electronic media possess some inherent advantages that make them unique in any teaching and learning process. One of numerous benefits is that they provide the teacher with interesting and compelling platforms for conveying information since they motivate learners to want to learn more and more. Also, by providing opportunities for private study and reference, the learner's interest and curiosity are increasingly stimulated. The use of electronic media can help in overcoming physical difficulties that could hinder effective presentation of a given topic. Generally, they make teaching and learning easier and less stressful. They are equally indispensable catalysts of social change and development.

Electronic media have become an integral part of our lives; they have changed our social habits and changed our perception of ourselves and the world around us - affecting human behaviour. Art does the same, even more, because it can provide

unexpected notions of the world and thus, provoke new insights. By utilising new media resources, it assists students to expand their creativity through digitally simulated information. Flexibility of digital data is what makes new media of vital importance for the teaching of Art. By using automated media tools and graphic software, students can quickly see the results of their ideas, and with the use of electronic media especially ICT, the amount of work in creating visual works is significantly reduced so that students will have more time for creativity, collaboration, research and assessment.

Before the end of the twentieth century, learning of Art has been mostly through textbooks, reproductions of works of art, various monographs about artists or encyclopedias and rare visits to museums. In the 21st century, the uses of electronic media have changed this narrative and this has brought revolutionary change into the teaching of Art. The rapid development of new expressive means of communication, the discovery of new media, the development of photography, film and television, new means of reproduction and modern technology have contributed to the fact that Art (in the sense of visual and communication expression) obtains completely new forms and dimensions in our century. Due to the interweaving, complementing and combined action of all these areas in this development, there (understandably) came about the enrichment of the expressive possibilities. Visual communications, as an irreplaceable medium for communication and expression, have become an integral part of our everyday life as they complement and accelerate the linguistic way of communication and their ability to express those relationships and values in spatial coordinates that the living or written word will never be able to express.

The use of electronic media facilities has become a necessity for improving quality in teaching and learning. The Federal Government of Nigeria also acknowledges this which is why the Federal Ministry of Education (FRN, 2010) emphasised that, electronic media is very important to the future of education in Nigeria. An efficient and effective successful implementation of electronic media in teaching will immensely contribute to meeting the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and Education for All (EFA) goals. The significant role of electronic media in classroom instructions is also attested to by the United Nations Education, Scientific and Cultural Organisations (UNESCO) at the Grunewald Declaration on Media in Germany, 1982. The declaration stated that “an increasing number of people spend time watching television, playing records and listening to the radio”. As such, bringing it to bear and form part of instruction that will be equally accepted by all.

To achieve Education for All (EFA), the Dakar 1990 Declaration called for improved teaching and learning facilities, and quality education for all learners and not only the best education for the best few (Abubakar, 2015). Bolujide (2016) opined that to achieve this goal, there should be a provision for adequate application of ICTs like video tapes, television and multimedia computer software that combine text, sound and colourful moving images which can be used to provide challenging and authentic content that will not only engage the student in the learning process but as well make learning concrete.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of this study is based on The Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning. The Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning was popularized by the work of Richard E. Mayer and other cognitive researchers who argue that multimedia supports the way the human brain learns. They assert that people learn more deeply from words and pictures than from words alone, which is referred to as the multimedia principle (Abubakar, 2015; Mayer 2005).

Literature Review

A lot of researches have been carried out on the significance of electronic media in capacity building and generally, in the teaching and learning processes. Adeloje (2021) assessed the attitudes of secondary school students in Akure south local government, Ondo state towards learning Art using ICT tools. The study adopted survey research design and a total of 200 students. Findings showed that both male and female students have a positive disposition towards learning Art using ICT tools. Similarly, Abubakar (2015) assessed the availability and utilisation of electronic media in teaching Social Studies in colleges of education in Nigeria using survey design. A sample of 1941 lecturers and students participated in the study and finding showed that most of the required electronic media for teaching and learning Social Studies were not available in the colleges; the available electronic media in the colleges were not adequately utilised for the teaching and learning of the subject.

Abdelraheem & Ahmed (2015) investigated the current use of social media as an electronic media and its benefits in teaching and learning as well as the perception of barriers by Sudanese university faculty members. The study was a survey of a sample of 65 faculty members in Sudanese university and the finding showed that both male and female academic ranks are using social media tools and agreed that it has some benefits.

Objective of the Study

The primary objective of this study is to examine the utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition. The specific objectives of this study include to:

1. Examine the difference in the utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition between male and female teachers in Akwa Ibom state.
2. Examine the difference in the utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition between young and old teachers in Akwa Ibom state.
3. Examine the difference in the utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition based on the years of experience of the teachers.

Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What difference exists in the utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition between male and female teachers in Akwa Ibom State?
2. What difference exists in the utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition between young and old teachers in Akwa Ibom State?
3. What difference exists in the utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition based on the years of experience of the teachers?

Hypotheses

This study was guided by the following hypotheses stated in the null form.

1. There is no significant difference in the utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition between male and female teachers in Akwa Ibom state.
2. There is no significant difference in the utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition between young and old teachers in Akwa Ibom state.
3. There is no significant difference in the utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition based on the years of experience of the teachers.

Methodology

The descriptive survey design was adopted in the study. The area of this study was Akwa Ibom state. The population of this study comprised teachers in both secondary and tertiary levels of education in Akwa Ibom State. The study adopted the multistage random sampling approach with a sample of 500 teachers comprising 200 secondary school teachers, 100 lecturers of Colleges of Education and 200 lecturers in education faculties in public universities in Akwa Ibom State. The instrument entitled “Utilisation of Electronic Media for Artistic Skill Acquisition Questionnaire” (UEMASAQ) developed by the researcher was used in data collection. The instrument was divided into two sections: Section A comprised three items on the demographics of the respondents including their sex, age and years of experience.

Section B of the instrument comprised 20 items on the utilisation of the different electronic media for skill acquisition. All items on Section B were rated on four point Likert scale of strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree which were scored as 4,3,2,1 respectively. All negative items were scored in the reverse order of 1, 2, 3 and 4. The instrument was validated by experts and the reliability of the instrument yielded Cronbach Alpha of 0.73.

Data obtained were analysed using mean, standard deviation and independent t-test. All hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance and the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 27.0) was used to facilitate the data analysis. Out of the 500 copies of the questionnaire administered, 473 copies were retrieved. All statistical analyses were based on the 473 copies of the questionnaire retrieved.

Results

Research Question 1

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation showing differences in the utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill

Gander	N	Mean	Weighted mean score	Standard deviation
Male	230	37.37	1.87	8.05
Female	243	35.35	1.77	6.77

Data in Table 1 reveals that the mean score of 37.37 was obtained by male teachers on the utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill while their female counterparts obtained mean score of 35.35 with standard deviations of 8.05 and 6.77, respectively. The weighted mean scores of 1.87 and 1.77 were obtained on utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition, respectively. This result implies that the weighted mean score obtained by both male and female teachers were less than the expected weighted mean of 2.50 for a four point rating scale. This indicates low level of utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition. The result also shows that the weighted mean obtained by male was higher than that of the female (1.87 versus 1.77), indicating that the male utilised electronic media in artistic skill acquisition than their female counterparts.

Research Question 2

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation showing differences in the utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition by young and old teachers

Age (years)	n	Mean	Weighted mean score	Standard deviation
Young (less than 45)	275	37.03	1.85	7.76
Old teachers (Above 45)	198	35.36	1.77	0.50

Data presented in Table 2 reveal mean score of 37.03 on utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition by young teachers (less than 45 years) while old teachers (above 45 years) secured mean score of 35.36 on utilisation of electronic media for skill acquisition. Result shows that the young teachers secured a higher mean score on the utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition than old teachers. The weighted mean score of 1.85 was obtained by young teachers on utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition while old teachers obtained weighted mean score of 1.77 on utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition. Therefore, there is a better utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition by young teachers than aged ones. This means that there is a difference in the utilisation of utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition between young and old teachers.

Research Question 3

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation showing differences in the utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition based on teachers' years of experience

Years of experience	N	Mean	Weighted mean score	Standard deviation
Less than 10 years	273	37.12	1.88	7.98
10 years and above	200	35.26	1.76	6.61

Data presented in Table 3 show mean score of 37.12 on utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition by teachers with less than 10 years of working experience, while those with 10 years and above work experiences reported mean score of 35.26. The result indicates that teachers with less than 10 years of work experience had better utilisation of electronic media on artistic skill acquisition. This is also confirmed by the weighted mean score which was higher among teachers with less than 10 years of work experience than teachers with 10 years and above work

experience (1.88 versus 1.76). Therefore, there is a better utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition based on teachers' work experience.

Hypothesis 1

Table 4: Independent t- test result summary testing differences in the utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition between male and female teachers

Gender	n	Mean	Standard deviation	t-cal.	p-value	t-crit.
Male	230	37.37	8.05	2.957*	0.003	1.96
Female	243	35.34	6.77			

$n = 473$, $df = 471$, *significant at 5% ($p < 0.05$).

Data in Table 4 reveal that the t-cal of 2.957 is greater than the t-crit of 1.96 at the 0.05 level of significance with 471 degrees of freedom. The null hypothesis is, therefore, rejected which implies that there is a significant difference in the utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition between male and female teachers. Result shows that the male teachers reported better utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition than female teachers ($p < .05$).

Table 5: Independent t- test result summary testing differences in the utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition between young and old teachers

Age (years)	N	Mean	Standard deviation	t-cal.	p-value	t-crit.
Young (less than 45)	275	37.03	7.76	2.454*	0.015	1.96
Old (45 years and above)	198	35.36	6.99			

$n = 473$, $df = 471$, *significant at 5% ($p < 0.05$).

Data in Table 5 reveal that the t-cal of 2.454 is greater than the t-crit of 1.96 at the 0.05 level of significance with 471 degrees of freedom ($p < .05$). With this, the null hypothesis is rejected which implies that there is a significant difference in the utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition between young and old teachers. Result indicates that the young teachers reported better utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition than old teachers.

Table 6: Independent t- test result summary testing differences in the utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition based on teachers' years of experience

Years of experience	n	Mean	Standard deviation	t-cal.	p-value	t-crit.
Less than 10 years	273	37.12	7.98	2.763*	0.008	1.96
10 years and above	200	35.26	6.61			

$n = 473$, $df = 471$, *significant at 5% ($p < 0.05$).

Data in Table 6 shows that the t-cal of 2.763 is greater than the t-crit of 1.96 at the 0.05 level of significance with 471 degrees of freedom ($p < .05$). The null hypothesis is rejected which implies that there is a significant difference in the utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition based on teachers' years of experience. Result indicates that teachers with less than 10 years of experience reported better utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition than teachers with 10 years and above experience.

Discussion of the Findings

The primary purpose of this study was to examine the utilisation of electronic media in artistic skill acquisition. The study found that there is low level of utilisation of electronic media in artistic skill acquisition among teachers in Akwa Ibom State. Result also revealed that male teachers showed better level of utilisation of electronic media in artistic skill acquisition than their female counterparts ($p < .05$). Utilisation of electronic media in artistic skill acquisition was also found to be significantly higher among young teachers (age less than 45 years) than teachers who are 45 years and above. The study also established that teachers with less than 10 years of experience reported better utilisation of electronic media for artistic skill acquisition compared to teachers with 10 years and above work experience. The low level of utilisation of electronic media in artistic skill acquisition could be due to the problem of unavailability of electronic media in many schools and it is sure that one cannot utilise what is not available. This finding is corroborated by that of Abubkar (2015) who also established that low level of utilisation of electronic media among teachers is as a result of unavailability of these facilities. Another possible reason for this low level of utilisation could be as a result of lack of adequate training and retraining of teachers in the use of these technologies. This is consistent with the finding of Udoakah & Nda (2020) that absence of training is one of the major factors responsible for the low acquisition and utilisation of digital media in teaching and learning. The finding that showed that the young teachers had better utilisation of electronic media in artistic skill acquisition could be as a result of the fact that young people tend to have more for

digital media than the old teachers. They can easily adapt to meet the requirement as they are more likely to be exposed to electronic media than the old ones; this could also explain why years of experience was inversely proportional to the utilisation of electronic media in artistic skill acquisition.

Conclusion

This study has examined the utilization of electronic media in artistic skill acquisition and found that there is low level of utilisation of electronic media in artistic skill acquisition despite its numerous benefits. This may be attributed to the near absence of these facilities in schools as well as the lack of adequate training and support on how to deploy electronic media in artistic skill acquisition. The study also concludes that young teachers utilise electronic media in artistic skill acquisition than old teachers and this could be due to their ability to adapt to the digital age compared to the old teachers who may not have been exposed to the use of these facilities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following were recommended:

1. There is a need to make available necessary electronic media in all schools - both at secondary and tertiary levels so as to enhance the utilisation of electronic media in artistic skill acquisition for better performance of teachers and teaching effectiveness.
2. There is also a need for training and retraining of teachers on the use of electronic media in artistic skill acquisition.
3. Teachers also need to be enlightened on the benefits of using electronic media in artistic skill acquisition, most especially, in this 21st century where teaching and learning process has gone beyond the use of books, chalkboard and other traditional methods.
4. There is a need for government to create enabling environment that will foster the utilisation of electronic media for effective artistic skill acquisition.

References

- Abdelraheem, A. Y. & Ahmed, A.M. (2015). Electronic social media in teaching: Usages, benefits, and barriers as viewed by Sudanese faculty members. *American International Journal of Social Science*, 4(5), 58-68.
- Abubkar, A.J. (2015). Assessment of the availability and utilization of electronic media in teaching social studies in colleges of education in Nigeria. Unpublished PhD thesis, Department of Educational Foundation & Curriculum, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.

- Adeloye, A.A. (2021). Attitude of students towards teaching art and design using ICT tools in secondary schools in Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria. *Yıldız J Art Desg*, 8 (2): 75–80.
- Bolujide, O.J. (2016). Preponderance of ict in fine art (visual art) teaching and Learning in Nigeria. *European Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology*, 4(3): 1-15.
- Bullard, J. (2013). *How the Art Center Enhances Children’s Development*. Available at: <http://www.education.com/reference/article/art-center-enhances-children-development/?page=3> (accessed: 12/09/2023).
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2010). National policy on information technologies (ICT) in education.
- Kear, M., & Callaway, G. (2000). *Improving Teaching and Learning in the Arts*. London: Falmer Press.
- Koert, Robin Van (2000). Providing Content and Facilitating Social Change: Electronic Media and Rural Development Based on Case Material from Peru, First Monday , Vol. 5, No. 2, February; [www. Google .com](http://www.google.com) Search Engine, Accessed 12th September, 2023.
- Mayer, R. E. (2005). Cognitive theory of multimedia learning. In R.E. Mayer (Ed.), *The Cambridge handbook of multimedia learning*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Pintrich, P.R. & Schunk, D. (2002). *Motivation in education: Theory, research, and applications* (2nd E d.). Upper Saddle. NJ: Prentice-Hall, Inc.
- Riley, S. (2012). *Shake the Sketch: An Arts Integration Workbook*, US Copyright.
- Tsimboukidou, I. (2009). Pupils’ and teachers’ perceptions of visual art education: A case study based on one of Greece’s new secondary arts schools, Available at https://eric.exeter.ac.uk/repository/bitstream/handle/10036/3062/TsimboukidouI_Vol1.pdf (accessed: 16/07/2023).

Udoakah, N. & Nda, I.C. (2022). Acquisition and utilisation of digital media in the teaching and learning of mass communication in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *The Nigerian Journal of Communication (TNJC)*, 17(1): 81-100.

Udi & Nwosu (2023). Integrating Technologies in Education for Teaching and Learning of Fine Art in Nigeria, *Journal of Nigeria Association for Educational Media and Technology (JEMT)* 28 (1): 205-211